

Grief's Journey: a comparative Exploration in “The Stone Angel” and “The Diviners” by Margaret Laurence

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Abstract

Margaret Laurence's Manawaka series stands as a testament to the enduring exploration of human emotions, particularly the themes of mourning and grief. This paper extends the examination beyond "The stone Angel" and "The Diviners" to include additional novels within the series, such as "A Jest of God" and "The Fire Dwellers." Through the lens of various protagonists, including Rachel Cameron and Stacey mac aindra, Laurence delves into the intricate layers of grief, offering insights into its profound effects on individual psyche and interpersonal dynamics. By interweaving personal narratives with the broader social cultural context of Manawaka, Laurence captures the universal essence of mourning, portraying it not as a solitary journey but as a shared human experience. Furthermore the paper highlight's Laurence's own grappling with grief, as reflected in her literary endeavors, adding another dimension to the proration of this theme. Ultimately, Laurence's Manawaka series serves as a poignant reflection on the complexities of grief.

Keywords

Loss, Regret, Interpersonal Dynamics, Catharsis, Healing Journey, Psychological Impact, Inter Personal Dynamics.

Introduction

Margeret Laurence was Born in 1926 and raised in the Intimate embrace of Small Canadian town, Laurence's early life laid the foundation for her rebellious spirit against the confines of tradition. Margaret Laurence born as Jean Margaret weymss on July 18, in Nepewa, Manitoba, and passing away on January 5, 1987, in Lakefield , Ontario, stands as a monumental figure in Canadian women's literature. Her profound influence is marked by her ground breaking Novel's, " A Jest of God" and "The Diviners" both of which were honored with the Governor General's award for fiction. Beyond her notable contribution to novels, Laurence's talent extended to poetry, Short stories and children's literature, showcasing her versatility and in depth as a writer. Her commitment to the literary community went beyond her writing. Laurence played critical in establishing '**The writers Union of Canada**' demonstrating her dedication to supporting and advocating for writers across the country. Her leadership extended to academia as well, where she served as '**The chancellor of Trent University**, further solidifying her legacy in Canadian literature and education. In recognition of her significant contributions, she was appointed a companion of the order of Canada in 1972. Further cementing her legacy, the government of Canada named her a person of national historic significance in 2018, acknowledging her lasting impact on Canada's cultural heritage and the literary world. Laurence's works and her efforts in fostering a supportive environment for Canadian writers have left an indelible mark, making her a revered and inspirational figure in the annals of Canadian history.

Margaret Lawrence entered the world as the daughter of Robert wymss and Verna simpson. Tragedy struck early in her life when her mother passed away at the tender age of four, Margaret leading to her maternal aunt, Margaret Simpson, moving in to support the family. Simpson eventually married Robert, becoming Margaret's stepmother. Father loss came when Margaret was just nine years old, as her father passed away, leaving her to be raised primarily by her stepmother throughout her childhood. Margaret Lawrence suffer much due to death of her parents.

Jacques Derrida, "The work of the Themes of death dying, and the reaction to such losses generally encompassed by the term Mourning are significant in the history of literary expression." From a young age, showing early signs of her literary

talent.” Laurence began crafting short stories and poems by the age of seven, laying the groundwork for her future as celebrated author.

“Marked by personal losses and a triumphant return to Canada, Laurence’s resilience echoes in her characters, creating a narrative tapestry woven with threads of grief, strengths and introspection.”

In the Manawaka series by Margaret Laurence, mourning and grief emerges as central themes that permeate the narratives, offering profound insight into the human condition and the complexities of emotional experiences. Set in the fictional town of Manawaka, the series provides a rich tapestry of characters whose lives are deeply intertwined with the universal realities of loss, regret, and the search for meaning amidst adversity.

Laurence's exploration of mourning and grief in the Manawaka series is both poignant and multifaceted, encompassing a spectrum of emotions and experiences that resonate with readers on a deeply personal level, through her vivid prose and richly drawn characters, Laurence invites readers to enter into the depths of human sorrow and resilience, illuminating the ways in which grief shapes individual identity, relationships, and the fabric of community life in Manawaka. Throughout the series, Laurence delicately weaves a tapestry of sorrow and resilience.

Laurence deftly explores the ways in which grief reverberates through the fabric of community life in Manawaka. Through shared rituals, traditions, and collective moments of remembrance, characters find solace in each other's company, forging bonds of compassion and understanding amidst the pain of loss.

Mourning and grief serve as pivotal points in Margaret Laurence’s literary journey, where she delicately intertwines personal struggles with universal themes. Through her characters' experience of loss and bereavement, Laurence reflects her own inner turmoil and emotional struggles, infusing her narratives with raw authenticity and depth. Just as her characters grapple with complexities of grief, Laurence confronts her own demons, using her writing as cathartic outlet for processing her emotions and exploring the human condition.

Objective of study

1. Analyze the portrayal of mourning and grief in Margaret Laurence’s Manawaka Series.
2. Explore the impact of grief on individual identity and relationships within the narratives.
3. Highlight Margaret Laurence's personal engagement with grief as reflected in her literary works.

Review of Literature

A comparative review of mourning and grief in "The Stone Angel" and "The Diviners" offers a rich exploration of Margaret Laurence's thematic preoccupations across her manawaka series.

In "The stone Angel" grief is depicted as a deeply personal Journey undertaken by the protagonist, Hagar Shipley, as she confronts the inevitable losses and regrets of her life. Through Hagar's stoic yet introspective narration, Laurence delves into the complexities of mourning, revealing how the weight of unresolved grief shapes Hagar's relationship choices, and ultimately, her quest for redemption. The novel intricately weaves together themes of familial estrangement, the passage of time, and in viability of death.

In contrast, "The Diviners" offers a more expansive exploration of grief, weaving together the narrative of multiple characters against the backdrop of Canadian Prairie.

Through the characters of Morag Gunn, Laurence explores the intersection of personal and collective grief, highlighting the ways in which individual experiences of loss reverberate through communities and generations. Morag's journey of self discovery and reconciliation with her past mirrors the broader themes of cultural identity and the legacy of colonization offering a nuanced examination of the ways in which grief shapes both personal and cultural narrative.

Across both novels, Laurence's portrayal of grief is marked by its profound emotional resonance and its capacity to illuminate the complexities of the human condition. Through richly draw characters and evocative prose, Laurence invites readers to confront the inherent pain and beauty of mourning challenging them to reckon with the ghosts of their own pasts and the impermanence of life itself.

Main Text

The Stone Angel:- "The Stone Angel by Margaret Laurence is a poignant novel that follows the life of Hagar Shipley, an elderly woman reflecting on her past as she approaches death. The story is set in the fictional town of Manawaka, Manitoba, and spans several decades, from Hagar's childhood to her final days in a nursing home. The novel begins with Hagar's recollections of her youth, growing up as the daughter of Jason Currie, wealthy and stern man who has high expectations for his children. Despite her father's disapproval, Hagar rebels against societal expectations and asserts her independence. She married Brampton Shipley, a poor farmer, against her father's wishes, and the marriage is marked by mourning and grief.

The death of Hagar Shipley's mother, Sarah Currie, represents a significant loss in her life, marking a pivotal moment in her emotional journey. While the novel does not delve deeply into the immediate aftermath of Sarah's death, its impact on Hagar is profound and enduring. The loss of her mother leaves Hagar grappling with a complex mix of emotions, including grief, longing, and a sense of displacement. As she navigates life without her mother's presence, Hagar confronts feelings of emptiness and nostalgia for the comfort and security of maternal affection. Sarah's absence serves as a constant reminder of the fleeting nature of human existence and the inevitability of loss, prompting Hagar to reflect on the fragility of life and the impermanence of familial bonds. Moreover, Hagar's struggle after the death of her mother is compounded by the strained relationships within her family, particularly with her father, Jason Currie, whose domineering presence looms large in her life. In the aftermath of her mother's death, Hagar embarks on a journey of self-discovery and emotional reckoning, seeking solace in moments of solitude and reflection. The death of Hagar Shipley's mother serves as a poignant reminder of the profound impact of loss on the human psyche and the enduring quest for understanding and connection amidst the pain of separation and longing.

Hagar's brother Dan's death prompts Hagar to reflect on the dynamics of her family and the complexities of sibling relationships. She cherishes memories of their shared past, including moments of conflict and tension, as well as instances of fleeting connection and understanding.

Dan's absence leaves a void in Hagar's life, contributing to her sense of loneliness and isolation. Despite their tumultuous relationship, Dan was a significant presence in Hagar's life, and his death leaves her feeling adrift and disconnected from her family and her past. Hagar struggles to find closure in the wake of Dan's death, as she grapples with unresolved issues and unspoken emotions surrounding their relationship. This lack of closure exacerbates her sense of grief and regret, leaving her longing for understanding and reconciliation that can never be fully realized.

The death of Hagar Shipley's father Jason Currie, marks a significant moment in her life and influences her emotional journey. While Hagar's relationship with her father is marked by tension and conflict, his death represents a form of liberation for her. Jason's domineering presence loomed large in Hagar's life, and his passing frees her from the constraints of his authority, allowing her to assert her independence and autonomy more fully. Jason's death prompts Hagar to reflect on the dynamics of her family and the complexities of her relationship with her father. Despite their strained bond, Jason was a central figure in Hagar's life, and his absence leaves a void that forces her to confront her own identity and sense of self within the context of her family history. Hagar's feelings about his father's death are complex and multifaceted, while she experiences a sense of relief at being freed from his control, she also grapples with feelings of guilt, regret, and unresolved anger. Jason's death brings forth a flood of conflicting emotions for Hagar, challenging her perceptions of love, duty, and familial obligation. Jason's death raises questions about inheritance and legacy within the Currie family. As Hagar navigates the aftermath of her father's passing, she confronts issues of inheritance and familial responsibility, grappling with the legacy of her father's wealth and expectations placed upon her as his daughter.

"Grief is like a river, finds its own course through the land & shape of our lives"
(Laurence, *The Diviners*.)

The death of Hagar Shipley's husband, Bram Shipley, brings forth a cascade of struggles, regrets, and grief for Hagar. Bram's death leaves Hagar grappling with a profound sense of loss and loneliness. Despite their strained marriage, Bram was a significant presence in Hagar's life, and his absence leaves her feeling adrift and disconnected from her past and her sense of identity. Hagar's relationship with Bram is marked by conflict, resentment, and unfulfilled expectations. His death brings forth a flood of unresolved tensions and unspoken emotions for Hagar, including guilt over the breakdown of their marriage and regrets about missed opportunities for connection and understanding. Despite the difficulties in their relationship, Hagar mourns the loss of the potential for

reconciliation and redemption that Bram's death represents. She grapples with feelings of sadness and longing for the love and connection that she never fully experienced in her marriage, adding another layer of complexity to her grief. Bram's death also brings practical challenges for Hagar, including financial insecurity and uncertainty about her future. As she navigates the aftermath of Bram's passing, Hagar must confront issues of inheritance, property rights, and her own ability to support herself independently, adding additional layers of stress and anxiety to her grief.

Bram's death prompts Hagar to reflect on the complexities of marriage and family dynamics. She confronts memories of their shared history, including moments of joy and sorrow, and wrestles with questions about the nature of love, commitment, and forgiveness in the context of their relationship.

“In the tapestry of life, grief is the thread that binds us all together, weaving a common bond of humanity.” (Laurence, *The Stone Angel*, 1964)

The death of Hagar Shipley's son in "The Stone Angel" represents one of the most harrowing and profound sources of grief and turmoil in her life, underscoring deep themes of loss, regret, and the struggle to find place amidst tragedy. The loss of a child is an unimaginable tragedy for any parent, and for Hagar, it is a devastating blow that brings her profound grief. This grief permeates her existence, casting a long shadow over her remaining days and coloring her reflections on her life and relationships. Hagar's sorrow is compounded by feelings of regret and self-blame. She ruminates on what might have been done differently, questioning her decisions and actions as a mother. This introspection often leads to a painful cycle of regret, where she wonders if her own shortcomings contributed to her son's demise.

The death of her son exacerbates Hagar's sense of isolation, both emotionally and, at times, physically from those around her. Grieving deeply, she often finds it difficult to connect with others who are still in her life, feeling that the chasm created by her loss is too vast to bridge.

Accepting the loss of her son is a significant challenge for Hagar. Throughout "The Stone Angel" her journey is one of struggling to come to terms with this loss, to find a place for it within her heart that doesn't completely consume her with sorrow and bitterness.

The death of her son also affects the dynamics within the remaining family, bringing to the surface underlying tensions, unresolved conflicts, and the pain of shared loss. It tests the bonds of family, sometimes straining them to their limits, while at other moments, it serves as a bitter glue that holds the surviving members together in shared mourning. In the wake of such a monumental loss, Hagar seeks meaning and continuity in her life. This often involves a painful reevaluation of her beliefs, her values, and the legacy she wishes to leave behind. It's a quest to find some sense or resolution in the face of an irrevocable separation from her son.

Hagar's struggle to express her grief openly is influenced by cultural expectations of emotional restraint. This societal norm compels her to internalize her pain, leading to a complex, often solitary mourning process that exacerbates her isolation. The expectations placed on women to be the caretakers of family.

Hagar's social status and the expectations of propriety and dignity associated with it further influence her mourning. The need to maintain a facade of strength and control in public, even in the face of devastating loss, highlights how societal pressures can dictate the ways in which grief is publicly acknowledged and expressed.

The novel also touches on how cultural and societal norms of grief are passed down through generations. Hagar's own attitudes towards mourning are shaped by the precedents set by her parents, and in turn, she influences her children's perceptions of grief and mourning. The physicality of grief and mourning is a significant theme that interweaves through the narrative, reflecting the protagonist Hagar Shipley's internal and external struggles. Hagar's journey is marked by the physical decline associated with aging, which parallels her experiences of grief and loss. Her stubbornness to remain independent despite her frailty and the physical challenges she faces underscores her internal struggle with the vulnerabilities brought about by grief and aging.

The physical limitations she encounters serve as constant reminders of her losses and the passage of time. Hagar's grief over the losses in her life, including the deaths of her son John and other family members, is deeply intertwined with her physical experience. Her emotional pain is often manifested physically, whether through tears that she fights

to hold back or through the sheer physical exhaustion that accompanies intense emotional distress.

Hagar's reluctance or care, especially from her daughter-in-law Doris, reflects her internal struggle with grief and her fear of dependency and loss of control. The physical setting of "The Stone Angel" often mirrors Hagar's internal state, with the harsh and unforgiving landscape of Manawaka reflecting her own emotional barrenness and physical challenges she faces.

The novel also explores the physical expressions of mourning through its depiction of funerals and Hagar's visits to the graves of loved ones. These moments highlight the societal rituals surrounding death and the physical acts of remembrance that are part of mourning process, offering contrast to Hagar's personal more internalized expression of grief.

The Diviners

In Margaret Laurence's "The Diviners" the themes of mourning and grief are central to the narrative, intricately woven into the life journey of the protagonist, Morag Gunn. Through Morag's Story, Laurence explores the complexities of grief, how it shapes Identity and creativity, and the ways in which individuals seek to find meaning and continuity in the face of loss. The novel presents a nuanced examination of mourning and grief, highlighting their transformative power and the indelible impact they have on an Individual's life.

Morag's experience of grief introduced early in the novel with the loss of her parents. This foundational bereavement marks the beginning of her journey through life, shaping her Identity and her quest for a sense of belongings. The mourning of her parents becomes driving force behind her need to understand her past and forge her Identity, illustrating how grief can motivate a search for meaning and self-discovery.

The complex relationship between Morag and her daughter, Pique, is another lens through which the novel explores grief. Pique's existence is a constant reminder of Morag's past choices and losses including her relationship with Pique Father, Jules Tonnerre. The dynamics between Morag and Pique reflect the ways in which grief and love are intertwined, and how mourning can be a process of coming to terms with the past and embracing the future.

"The Diviners" also addresses the theme of mourning in a broader scale, touching on the loss of cultural and historical Identity. Through the character of Jules and the stories of Métis community, Laurence delves into the grief, associated with the erosion of cultural heritage and the struggle to preserve identity in the face of societal marginalization. This collective mourning portrayed as both a personal and communal experience, highlighting the shared aspect of grief.

Morag career as a writer is depicted as a means of processing her grief and articulating her experiences. Her storytelling becomes an act of remembrance and away to give voice to her losses, underscoring the role of creativity in mourning.

Through her writing Morag, seeks to immortalize the people and experiences that have shaped her, suggesting that creative expression can be a powerful tool in the grieving process.

Much like in "The Stone Angel" the physical landscape in "The Diviners" mirrors the emotional landscape of the protagonist. The river that flows through the novel is a constant presence, symbolizing the flow of life and the inevitability of change. It serves as a metaphor for Morag's Journey through grief, representing the continuous process of loss, recovery and renewal. Ultimately, "The Diviners" portrays mourning and grief as transformative processes that, while painful can lead to growth, Self-understanding, and acceptance. Morag's Journey illustrates the possibility of finding a sense of wholeness and peace in the aftermath of loss, suggesting that the act of divining one's path through grief is an integral part of human experiences.

The separation from a spouse represents a profound point of grief deeply explored in literature and poignantly depicted Margaret Laurence's works, including "The Stone Angel" and "The Diviners" this type loss encompasses not only the physical absence of a partner but also the dissolution of shared dreams, the intimacy of companionship, and the identity formed within the partnership. The grief experienced from such a separation is

multifaceted, involving layers of emotional, psychological, and often financial and social ramifications.

“Grief is a journey, not a destination it is the path we walk in remembrance of those we've lost.” (Laurence, The Diviners, 1974)

The emotional turmoil following the separation from a spouse can be overwhelming. The separation of Morag Gunn from her husband, Brooke Skelton, marks a significant turning point in Morag's life, setting her on a path of self discovery, independence and ultimately, the embracement of her identity as a writer. This separation while painful, acts as a catalyst for Morag's personal growth and her deep exploration of grief and resilience. The Impact of this separation on Morag and her subsequent struggle with grief are multifaceted, touching upon emotional, social, and professional dimensions of her life. Morag's separation from Brooke is not just the end of a marriage but also a profound loss of the future they had envisioned together. This loss plunges her into a period of intense grief, characterized by feelings of loneliness, betrayal, and self doubt. Laurence delicately portrays Morag's internal turmoil, capturing the complexity of emotions that accompany the dissolution of a long term relationship. Morag's grief is compounded by the need to redefine her identity outside of the context of her marriage, challenging her to confront who she is as an individual and what she truly desires from life.

The separation also impact Morag socially and professionally. As a single mother in a society with rigid expectations about family structures, Morag faces stigma and isolation. Her role as a writer is both a refuge and a source of struggle, as she grapples with the demands of her career and the challenges of raising her daughter, Pique, alone. Laurence uses Morag's career as a lens through which to explore theme of female independence, highlighting the societal barriers women face in balancing personal ambition with care giving responsibilities.

“In the end, we mourn not only the loss of loved ones but also the loss of who we one were in their presence.” (Laurence, The diviners, 1974)

Conclusion

The exploration of mourning and grief in Margaret Laurence's "The Stone Angel" and "The Diviners" provides a profound commentary on the human condition, illuminating the universal experiences of loss, resilience and the quest for identity amidst the trials of life. Through the intricate narratives of Hagar Shipley in "The Stone Angel" and Morag Gunn in "The Diviners", Laurence delves deep into the heart of grief, portraying it not just as a response to death or separation but as a complex, transformative Journey that shapes the soul. In "The Stone Angel" Hagar's journey is one of reflection and reckoning, where the act of mourning becomes intertwined with a struggle for dignity and self-recognition against the backdrop of a life marked by pride and stubbornness independence. Hager's grief, stemming from the losses of her loved ones and the gradual erosion of her autonomy, is a mirror to her internal struggle with vulnerability and acceptance. **“In the depths of grief, we unearth the buried truths of our souls, confronting the shadows that haunt us even in the brightest of days” (Laurence, The store Angel, 1964).**

Through Hagar Laurence explores the themes of aging, memory, and the redemptive power of facing one's morality and past with courage and honesty.

Conversely, "The Diviners", presents a different yet equally compelling exploration of grief, focusing on Morag's experiences loss and separation as catalysts for personal growth and creative expression. Morag's journey through the landscapes of her life, marked by the departure from her husband and the challenges of single motherhood, reflects as a broader and narrative of seeking and defining Identity through the lens of loss. Her grief through deeply personal, also touches on universal themes of cultural dislocation, the search for belonging, and the heading power of storytelling.

Both novel, through their respective protagonists, underscores the inevitability of grief as part of the human experiences. The act of mourning, with all its pain and Introspection, can lead to a deeper understanding of oneself place in the continuum of life and death. Both Hagar and Morag, despite their differing circumstances and eras, represent strong, complex characters who challenges societal expectations and forge their own paths through the wilderness of their sorrow. Their stories are testaments to the strength of the human spirit to endure, to find meaning in suffering, and to emerge from the depth of grief with a renewed sense of purpose and identity.

In conclusion, Margaret Laurence "The Stone Angel" and "The Diviners" offer a rich, nuanced exploration of Mourning and grief, portrayed through the lives of characters who confront and transcend their suffering. These Characters not only bear witness to the pain

of loss but also celebrates the resilience and creativity with which individuals navigate their journeys of mourning, ultimately finding a way to reconcile with their past and embrace their future. Laurence's work remains poignant insightful contribution to Canadian literature, providing a lens through which to examine the complexities of grief and the indomitable will to survive and flourish in its aftermath.

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